

Low Defect Planar Graphene Exfoliation by Sonication in Polypropylene Carbonate and 5 sec Microwaving

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HIGHLIGHTS

- 1. This is the first study to exfoliate and synthesize 2D planar graphene from graphite with conformable with flat surfaces for electronic applications.**
- 2. Also the first study to synthesize low defect Graphene with smaller domain size, unobtainable by laboratory or industrially available arc discharge graphene production.**
- 3. Sonication in PPC happens by efficient transfer of cavitation pressures, by PPC- π interaction at the basal planes.**
- 4. 5 sec microwave thermal expansion and relaxation of individual graphene sheets, reduces domain size, increases π -configuration and planar properties.**

Abstract: This is an exceptional process on low cost, low defect and high-quality graphene which is produced by sonication in PPC and microwaving for just 5sec. Low energy arc-discharging process expands electrolytic graphite rods into hierarchical-like 3D- graphene retaining the basal plane carbon crystalline order and chemical purity. Sonication in Polypropylene Carbonate causes non-covalent PPC- π bonding at graphene basal plane,

aligning the graphene sheets in directions that allows efficient transmission of cavitation pressures and exfoliation; while microwave treatment for 5s separates any layered graphene, utilizing thermally induced lattice vibrations without changes on surface properties. Produced graphene (XRD $2\theta = 26^\circ\text{C}$) has low defect ($0.05 < \text{ID/IG} < 0.2$), retainment of chemical purity (0~2.5% ΔO_2 content), with optimized effective graphene sizes (ranging from 350nm to 35 μm), for diverse applications, dispersibility in diverse solvent, conformability to flat semi-transparent surfaces; storable in concentrated slurry ($>50 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$).

Keywords: *Low defect; 2D Planar; arc discharge graphene; PPC sonication; 5 sec microwaving; exfoliation; electronics.*

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